

HEALTH SYSTEM AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE OF PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN BATANGAS PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

In highly volatile and uncertain times, organizations need to develop a resilience capacity which enables them to cope effectively with unexpected events, bounce back from crisis and foster future success. This study intended to deepen the understanding of the public health system and the embedded construct of resilience of public hospitals in the province of Batangas. Using a questionnaire adapted from the Health System Rapid Diagnostic Tool (2012) and Organizational Resilience Capability Assessment (2016), the study aimed to come up with a typology of the public hospitals in the province based on their health system and organizational resilience. Results revealed that public hospitals in the province of Batangas have a good achievement in the standards of health workforce while fair achievement in terms of service delivery, information, financing, medicines and leadership and governance. It was also found out that the public hospitals have a defined level of resilience and that there is a significant relationship between the health system and organizational resilience. Based on the focus group discussion, the challenges encountered by the public hospitals match the gaps in resources and governance. Lastly, eight public hospitals in the province of Batangas were classified as developing and three as progressive. Health interventions and strategies were also developed to improve resilience during health emergencies and achieve sustainable transformations in the field of health care delivery.

Keywords: health system, organizational resilience, explanatory sequential, typology, Philippines